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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYA NARAYANAN bearing USN6SU21FS001 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISHWARYA bearing USN6SU21FS002 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA S S bearing USN6SU21FS003 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALINA GEORGE bearing USN6SU21FS004 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANKITHA BRUNETTE DSOUZA bearing USN6SU21FS005 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHITHA bearing USN6SU21FS006 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BAVITHA J bearing USN6SU21FS007 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHETHAN SKANDA S J bearing USN6SU21FS008 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANALAKSHMI D bearing USN6SU21FS009 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAIZ AHMED bearing USN6SU21FS010 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JUNAINA KUNNUKATTIL NASEER bearing USN6SU21FS011 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LANKESH K B bearing USN6SU21FS012 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MALAVIKA ANAND bearing USN6SU21FS013 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MITASHREE M M bearing USN6SU21FS014 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAIK MEGHANA RAGUNATH bearing USN6SU21FS015 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDAN RAVI bearing USN6SU21FS016 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRACHI PONNAMMA M K bearing USN6SU21FS017 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAVEEN CHANDRAN bearing USN6SU21FS018 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAGEE RAJAN bearing USN6SU21FS019 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAHUL UDAY KUMAR SHETTY bearing USN6SU21FS020 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SINDHUSAGAR R bearing USN6SU21FS021 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA A bearing USN6SU21FS022 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAMSHI S KOTIAN bearing USN6SU21FS023 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIJAY JAISON bearing USN6SU21FS024 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms YASHWIN S SALIYAN bearing USN6SU21FS025 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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